

EDUCATIONAL TRANSFORMATION IN THE DIGITAL ERA: THE IMPACT OF LEARNING FROM HOME PROGRAMS, EMPLOYEE INNOVATION AND PUBLIC SERVICE MOTIVATION ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

This article investigates the transformation of education in the digital era and its impact on employee performance with a focus on the implementation of learning programs from home, employee innovation and public service motivation. The digital era has changed the educational landscape significantly, including the implementation of home learning programs as a response to extraordinary events. Employee innovation and public service motivation also have an important role in influencing employee performance in facing change. This study used a quantitative approach, the sample size was 297 out of 1323 population of Serang City Junior High School teachers, and the sampling technique was using the Krijce table. Hypothesis testing was carried out using SEM (*Structural Equation Modeling*) analysis. Data were collected through a questionnaire that measured employee perceptions of the implementation of learning programs from home, the level of innovation shown by employees, and their motivation for public service. Employee performance data is also analyzed based on relevant indicators. The results of this research identify that the home learning program has a positive impact on employee performance. Employee innovation also has a significant effect on employee performance, where employees who are more likely to be innovative achieve better performance. Apart from that, public service motivation has also been proven to be positively related to employee performance, showing that motivation to contribute to society and institutions influences employee performance.

Keywords: Transformation, BDR Program Implementation, Employee Innovation, Public Service Motivation, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The digital era has brought significant changes in the way we access, manage and convey information. Transformation in education in the digital era is not only related to technological developments but also involves shifts in the paradigm of learning, teaching and educational management. One very important aspect of this transformation is the implementation of distance learning programs, which has become an increasingly urgent need when facing extraordinary situations such as the global pandemic. Technology has also become crucial during times of isolation and social distancing, being used to support and maintain student well-being through online learning (Goldschmidt, 2020). For this reason, it is important for all educational institutions, teachers and students to actively utilize technology and increase their understanding of digital literacy. This is necessary so that they can continue to follow

developments in all aspects of educational institutions, as well as face the challenges that arise in the reality of education in the digital era (Edeh Michael Onyema et al., 2020). Information and communications technology (ICT), especially in the context of teachers' digital competencies and the educational opportunities they have to improve those competencies, is becoming a critical factor in adapting to the shift to online learning (Dhawan, 2020; König et al., 2020). In the context of digital education, employee innovation and motivation in public services also have a significant role in efforts to improve employee performance.

The importance of implementing distance learning programs as a response to emergencies such as the COVID-19 pandemic has changed the traditional paradigm in education. Teachers and students need to adapt to a different environment, where physical interaction is limited and technology is the main tool in delivering learning material. Implementing the home learning policy requires innovation in teaching methods, learning media and learning processes. This is a demand that forces teachers, students and parents to develop new patterns of thinking and action in the educational context (Ionescu et al., 2020; Mladenova et al., 2020; Müller, 2021). In this context, understanding the contribution of implementing distance learning programs to the transformation of education and the performance of teaching staff in the digital era is very important. This transformation process cannot be realized without innovation on the part of teachers. The use of effective teaching methods in a digital environment requires innovation from teachers, which includes not only technological aspects, but also includes the development of creative learning approaches, sophisticated interaction strategies, and efficient content management.

However, there are several challenges faced in this context, such as a lack of technological knowledge, limited time and professional resources in supporting online learning, internet access costs, and the additional burden for parents in accompanying children in the learning process. Therefore, teachers are expected to be more innovative in choosing learning materials and to be more creative in designing learning strategies that suit students' needs (Ayu et al., 2020). The effectiveness of online education depends heavily on learning design, the use of technology in the educational process, the quality of teacher teaching, and the individual characteristics of students (Fauziyah, 2020; Jamal, 2020; Purbawati et al., 2020; Wardany et al., 2021).

Moreover, employee motivation in public service is a factor that has a significant impact on their overall commitment to providing quality education for students. The concept of public service motivation, defined by several researchers such as (Christensen et al., 2017; Crewson, 1997; Perry, 2018; Wright, 2007), is a commonly used framework for analyzing civil servant behaviour and demonstrating that individual values and needs must be in line with the mission of the public organization.

Apart from that, one important component that is expected to improve the quality of implementing online education is teacher performance. Teacher performance reflects the process and results of their work in carrying out tasks based on their professional responsibilities in managing learning to achieve educational goals, especially during the pandemic and the implementation of online learning policies. Several studies such as those

conducted by (Baso Intang Sappailee, Patahuddin, 2022; Hadiati, 2022). has emphasized the important role of teacher performance in the implementation of online education. Therefore, the role of teacher performance has a significant impact, where increasing teacher performance can potentially increase the overall success of implementing online education.

This study aims to measure the impact of implementing distance learning programs and innovations implemented by employees, through their motivation in public service, on employee performance in the digital era. Through this research analysis, it is hoped that a deeper understanding will be obtained of the interactions between these factors and how these interactions affect employee performance in supporting changes in the field of digital education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The quantitative approach was chosen for this study because the method allows the measurement of research variables and testing of hypotheses through statistical analysis, as suggested by (Neuman, 2006). Quantitative research is confirmatory, which involves collecting and managing primary data from respondents' answers after distributing the questionnaires, then interpreting the results of the research to confirm or compare with the results of previous studies. Neuman also suggests that surveys can be conducted using formal questionnaires or interviews to collect information from a large number of respondents, which can include a variety of backgrounds, attitudes, or personalities. This research sample consisted of 297 responses from 1323 teachers at Serang Junior High School (SMP), and the sampling technique was based on the Krejcie table. In this study, data was collected through a structured questionnaire containing a series of questions. Respondents were asked to provide responses related to implementing BDR policies, employee innovation, public service motivation (PSM), and employee performance. To analyze the data, the SEM (*Structural Equation Modeling*) method is used to classify variables that can be measured and variables that cannot be measured.

DISCUSSION

Educational Transformation in the Digital Era

Technological advances have fundamentally changed the way we teach and learn. Implementing a distance learning program is a very important alternative when unexpected events occur that disrupt normal school operations. With access to online learning platforms, students have more flexibility in accessing learning materials. However, this change also brings new challenges for educators in creating a more interactive and effective learning environment in the digital era. There are differences in learning approaches between those who were born and grew up in the digital era (digital native generation) and those who learned about technology later in life (digital immigrant generation) (Prensky, 2001). Therefore, teachers must have sufficient understanding and skills in integrating technology into the learning process (Mishra & Koehler, 2006) to increase the effectiveness of learning from home. Technological developments in the context of distance education include digital transformation in learning methods, the growth of distance education, and innovation in the learning process

(Johnson, L., Adams Becker, S., Estrada, V., and Freeman, 2015). Educational transformation in the digital era involves various factors, including technology, leadership, and changes in the curriculum (Fullan, 2007).

In the context of the Study at Home program which is faced during extraordinary events such as the Covid-19 pandemic, digital education transformation includes the adoption of technology and online learning platforms as an alternative to traditional face-to-face education. This transformation changes the conventional learning paradigm by utilizing technology to provide more flexible access and learning experiences (Greenhow et al., 2016). The impact of digital transformation on the entire teaching and learning process, from its initial conception to becoming a central element in education, has become a major focus of research (Fullan, 2007).

Effective teacher professional development involves a variety of approaches and techniques that can provide positive results in terms of teaching and learning effectiveness (Darling-hammond et al., 2017). The aim of education today is to be able to adapt to the needs and demands of the 21st-century world and to reflect the changes in the educational paradigm needed to produce individuals who are ready to face the dynamics and opportunities in the modern world. Therefore, the role of technology and educational transformation is very important, with technology being used as a tool to enhance the learning process and prepare students for a changing future (Prensky, 2016). The transformation of education in the digital era, especially those related to home learning programs, has brought about fundamental changes in the learning model.

Implementation of the Learning From Home (BDR) program during extraordinary events

Public policy implementation theory provides an in-depth understanding of how public policy is implemented in practice, including in the context of home study programs. Pülzl and Treib (2017) explain that public policy implementation refers to concrete steps taken to implement or implement an agreed public policy, using specific tools or means, to achieve the policy objectives. In this context, policy implementation is a practical stage that is different from the more theoretical policy formulation process.

Public policies that are formulated usually have goals or targets to be achieved. However, this goal can only be achieved if the policy is implemented. Therefore, policy implementation is an important stage in the public policy cycle and can determine the extent to which the policy is successful or not. Policy implementation involves the interaction between goals and actions taken by individuals or groups, both in the government and private sectors, which aim to achieve the goals set in the policy (Pülzl & Treib, 2017). The top-down perspective on policy implementation, developed by Edwards III. & George (1980), identified four main variables that greatly influence the successful implementation of a policy, namely communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure.

The implementation of the Learning from Home (BDR) program policy during Extraordinary Circumstances (KLB) caused by the Covid-19 pandemic involves various approaches, including distance learning (PJJ) through online platforms, face-to-face learning (offline), and

learning through visits to student's home (home visit). These steps were taken by the government to stop the spread of the Covid-19 virus and also to fulfil children's right to education. First, there is the online or distance learning model, which has become the norm during the Covid-19 pandemic. Second, there is a face-to-face learning model that can be implemented in schools that are in green zones (areas with low virus transmission rates) or in remote areas that do not have internet access and have low virus transmission rates. The third model is learning through visits to students' homes, known as home visits. The policy of learning from home implemented through online learning is something new in the world of education, especially at the junior high school level. As an innovation, of course, this policy faces various problems and challenges during the implementation process.

As the main implementer in implementing distance learning programs, teachers have a very crucial role in overcoming various challenges faced by students. In this context, teachers must have the flexibility and creativity to develop learning models and strategies that suit the characteristics of students in their schools. The use of various applications in online learning is a very useful tool for teachers in the learning process. As expressed by Lipsky (2010) , the concept of "street-level bureaucrats" refers to individuals who act as policy implementers on the front lines, and they often have to interpret ambiguous policies in their implementation. In the educational context, teachers are real examples of street-level bureaucrats, as they interact directly with the students and communities they serve. Teachers' duties include not only meeting students' academic needs but also paying attention to the special demands and priorities that exist in their communities (Cohen & Hertz, 2020). As explained by Gofen and Lotta (2021) , street-level bureaucrats have an important role as the front guard in providing public services and play a significant role in the government's response to crises and emergencies. In the context of distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers have become agents who play a similar role as policy implementers on the front lines, with the important task of supporting students' education and welfare amidst the challenges they face.

Online learning refers to the formal learning process carried out by educational institutions, where students and teachers are physically separated. To support this learning, we need an interactive communication system that connects the two parties. The basic theory in online education is often referred to as online participation theory, which emphasizes the importance of participation in online learning as an integral part of the educational process (Hrastinski, 2009). Participation in online learning does not only include speaking or writing but also involves various activities that support the learning process. Online learning opens opportunities for students to study flexibly, without being bound by time or location restrictions. At SMP Kota Serang, the implementation of the Learning from Home (BDR) program involves developing a distance learning platform and utilizing digital technology. Teachers are responsible for designing effective and interesting learning materials, as well as managing interaction and communication with students through digital media. While this program presents challenges, it also opens up new opportunities to provide high-quality education in unusual settings.

In the context of implementing a home study program, communication is a very important key factor. This policy must be communicated effectively to all relevant parties, and resources play a significant role in the implementation process. Organizational characteristics also play a role in the implementation of this policy, with the involvement of staff and related parties in the planning and implementation of the Learning from the Home program being a very important factor. Apart from that, the environment also has a significant influence on the implementation of this program.

H₁: Implementation of the Learning From Home program influences community service motivation

Policy implementation refers to the implementation of policy decisions which are usually described in a policy document, although it can also be expressed through executive directives or other important policy decisions. Ideally, these decisions will identify the problems that need to be solved, define the expected results, and detail the implementation process in various ways (Sabatier & Mazmanian, 1985). Policy implementation is a series of actions taken by the government or the private sector, both individually and collectively, to achieve the goals set out in the policy. In this context, policy implementation is a means of making a policy effective in achieving its goals (Nugroho R, 2014).

Public service motivation can be defined as an individual's drive to support unique organizational and group motives, as well as intrinsic motives related to the desire to make a positive contribution to beneficial program outcomes (Song et al., 2017). This research shows that policy implementation can increase employee motivation in providing public services so that it becomes a way for employees to develop themselves and implement the Learning From Home program more effectively. Public service motivation is an encouragement that encourages individuals to contribute to efforts to improve the welfare of society or to carry out work that is oriented towards public service. If the Learning From Home program provides stimulating and supportive learning facilities, such as a stable internet connection, this will provide additional motivation for teachers to carry out their duties.

The standard regression coefficient for the effect of Home Learning (BDR) program implementation on Public Service Motivation (PSM) is 0.057, with a critical ratio that exceeds 1.96, namely 5.479. These results indicate that the implementation of the BDR program has a significant influence, with an estimate of 0.312, on Public Service Motivation. In the context of implementing home learning policies, it is recognized that Public Service Motivation possessed by employees (teachers) has the potential to influence the implementation of the BDR program, which consists of various dimensions and indicators. The most significant first dimension is disposition, with the smallest indicator being "supervising activities" (0.799), while the largest indicator is "carrying out training" (0.868). The second dimension is bureaucratic structure, which is based on indicators such as "interdependence of instructions between program implementation" (0.815), "division of tasks and responsibilities" (0.847), and "standards and procedures in implementation" (0.863). The third dimension is resources, with indicators such as "the existence of competent employees capable of carrying out tasks" (0.825), "completeness of facilities and infrastructure" (0.830), "provision of needs" (0.849),

and "authority to prepare plans according to needs" (0.880). The fourth dimension is communication, with indicators such as "conformity of message content" (0.915), "creation of accurate regulations" (0.972), "distribution of opportunities to employees" (0.976), and "dissemination of information" (0.979).

So that the implementation of the Learning from Home program has a complex impact on employee performance at SMP Kota Serang. Teachers with high Public Service Motivation tend to be more motivated to overcome the challenges faced in implementing this program because they feel they have a responsibility towards students and the community. Public Service Motivation is a key factor in how teachers deal with changes in implementing learning from home. Teachers with strong Public Service Motivation tend to be more proactive in finding solutions to emerging challenges, work harder to ensure the continuity of student education and maintain good communication with parents. To increase the positive impact of the implementation of the Learning from Home with Public Service Motivation program at junior high schools in the city of Serang, it is necessary to adopt a holistic approach. This includes training for the development of technology skills, psychological and managerial support, and recognition and reward for teacher efforts. Thus, the result of implementing the Learning from Home program can create better employee performance and support sustainable education goals.

Employee Innovation

In facing the changes and challenges of the digital era, employee innovation is a very crucial aspect. Innovation in the education sector includes the development of new learning methods, the use of technology, and creative approaches to the teaching process. This innovation not only aims to increase efficiency in the learning process but also opens up new opportunities to improve the overall quality of education.

In the context of learning-from-home policies, employee innovation refers to the ability of employees, including teachers, to create and implement new ideas that can increase the effectiveness and efficiency of implementing learning-from-home programs. In situations where the Learning from Home program is implemented, innovation becomes a very important factor. Teachers must adapt to new ways of delivering learning materials to students by ensuring that the material content complies with the guidelines and policies that apply in the Learning from Home program.

Innovation is the process of creating and implementing new ideas, processes, products, services or methods that bring about tangible improvements in terms of efficiency, effectiveness or quality of results. Research by Mulgan and Albury (Ec Albury) illustrates that the understanding of innovation has undergone a significant change from the initial concept which was more limited, and only focused on products and processes. Product or service innovation involves transformation in form and design, while process innovation involves continuous improvement in quality or service. It also includes the transformations in the organizations, procedures and policies needed to support innovation.

The concept of innovation can have various meanings depending on the perspective of the expert who studies it. In general, innovation can be explained as the introduction of new technology that has economic value or a new combination of existing technologies to create a significant change in the relationship between value and price provided to customers or users. (De Meyer & Garg, 2005). In the context of public sector management, according to AV Anttiroiko, (2014) Innovation can be defined as the successful application of new mechanisms or organizations to overcome management problems or achieve better management results. Apart from that, according to West (2000) in Im, Campbell, and Jeong (2016), innovation can also refer to the development of new, more efficient methods for completing various tasks in the work environment. In the context of teachers at Junior High Schools in Serang City, employee innovation refers to their creative efforts in implementing the Learning from Home program and adapting traditional teaching methods to make them more effective.

In general, according to Mori (2009), innovation is seen as a new idea a new way of doing something or a change that improves service quality. Innovation is the implementation of new or useful ideas (Lee et al., 2020). According to Im, Campbell, and Jeong (2016) employee innovation variable is measured by three items adopted from the scale developed by Scott et al. (1994) : employees are creative; responsiveness to change; and the availability of resources to implement new initiatives. To improve the quality of education and the delivery of teaching, teachers must become innovators, because innovation is the main tool for individual development, economic growth and national development. Innovation in education can emerge when new teaching techniques, modern learning processes, contemporary teaching tools or new institutional structures are implemented to bring about substantial transformation in learning and teaching, leading to better student learning for greater efficiency and productivity (Rafique et al ., 2021).

Public service motivation generally refers to an individual's drive to provide services to others with the good intention of contributing to society at large. Thus, Public Service Motivation (PSM) is defined as an individual's tendency to be specifically involved in that service in the context of a public organization. Likewise, the learning process is carried out during extraordinary events such as COVID-19, where the learning carried out is a learning process from home with or without technological media. So with a high PSM educators (teachers and principals) will be more innovative in learning activities. Hsu and Tung-Wen Sun (2014) stated that PSM can be an integral part of the intrinsic motivation of public services. PSM can also reflect professionalism and professional training which encourages bureaucrats to adapt to the rules (Kwon, 2014). In March 2020 the discovery of Covid-19 cases prompted the education sector to carry out distance learning to ensure continuous teaching and learning (Moluayonge, 2020). Therefore, the government issued a policy in the education sector through the BDR process in Serang City, which appealed to educators to innovate to ensure education remains inclusive and accessible so that learning from home is not limited to online distance education. Some media are utilized, such as the use of government-issued television as part of a distance education program, known as "learning from home". This program emphasizes literacy, numeracy, and character development for all primary and secondary school levels. However, its implementation is hampered by problems such as inequality in internet access, gaps in

teacher qualifications and education quality, as well as lack of access to education. lack of proficiency in information and communication technology (Joaquin et al., 2020).

H₁: The implementation of the Learning from Home program affects public service motivation

This study obtains a standard regression weight for the effect of innovation on Public Service Motivation (PSM) of 0.069, with a critical ratio value greater than 1.96, which is 2.776. Thus, it can be concluded that innovation has a significant influence on public service motivation. The estimated value of 0.221 indicates that the impact of innovation on PSM has a significant regression coefficient. The results of this study support the findings of previous studies which also show that individuals with higher PSM levels tend to be more innovative. This means that innovation is often initiated by individuals or teachers who have high PSM levels. This high level of PSM is related to the development of relevant dimensions and indicators.

This research also strengthens the findings previously made by Hsu & Tung-Wen Sun, (2014); Rafique et al., (2021); Rosa et al., (2020); Suong, (2021) which shows that individuals with high PSM tend to be more innovative. In the context of the theory developed by Scott et al. (1994) in Im, Campbell, this study identified changes in the value of indicators from low to high levels in the factors that influence employee innovation.

In particular, this study shows that factors such as the use of available resources (0.820) and the availability of financial resources (0.878) are important factors in increasing innovation. Furthermore, factors such as providing creative ideas in carrying out activities (0.845) and the ability to convey new ideas and convince others (0.901) also have a significant contribution to increasing innovation.

In the context of the current digital era, innovation is very important in the development of new and effective technology and teaching methods. Innovation can influence employee performance by increasing efficiency and effectiveness in providing services. The role of the teacher as an innovator is crucial in developing adaptive and innovative learning methods in implementing the Learning From Home program. They need to create inspiring content, develop effective teaching tools, and overcome technological barriers. Employee innovation includes the ability to respond to change with creativity, create new solutions, and adapt to an ever-changing learning environment. This also includes the ability to adopt new technology-based learning methods.

Public Service Motivation

Public service motivation is a factor that greatly influences employee performance in carrying out educational functions. In the educational context, public service motivation includes enthusiasm and positive contributions to society. This motivation encourages employees to innovate, adapt and carry out their duties wholeheartedly.

Perry and Wise (1990), as cited in (Vandenabeele, 2014), define PSM as an individual tendency to have special motives for certain public institutions. PSM in this view is a form of dedication to public service, community needs, or general welfare, which is based on intrinsic motivation (Ryu, 2017). More specifically, Perry and Wise (1990) conclude that a large part of PSM is

related to the normative desire to serve the needs of society and social welfare as a whole. Zhu & Wu (2016) define public service motivation (PSM) as an individual's tendency to provide responses that include general and individual aspects of a public institution. In other words, PSM includes individual motivation to provide good and useful services to the community through these public institutions.

Perry and Wise (1990) in Fanhua Qi and Wang (2018) describe public service motivation as an individual tendency to have a distinctive or main motive in a public institution or organization. This is also in line with the views of Houston and Cartwright (2007), mentioned in Bozeman and Su (2015), that public service motivation assumes that public employees are community servants who are committed to the public interest. They are characterized by an ethic rooted in well-being, a passion for serving others, and a desire to influence the betterment of society. Public service motivation (PSM) according to Perry and Wise (1990) has several characteristics, namely an interest in the process of making public policies, a sense of responsibility for community needs and feelings as responsible citizens, empathy or compassion, and an attitude of sacrifice. Themselves in serving the public interest.

Public Service Motivation Theory (PSM) proposes an alternative approach to rational choice theory, which considers individuals as mere maximizers of personal interests, without considering obligations or moral values. This is more in line with the context of public organizations where goals are not always clearly defined and are often not directly linked to achieving personal goals (Zubair et al., 2021).

In the context of implementing the home learning program, public service motivation is reflected in the efforts of junior high school teachers in Serang City to provide educational services to the community. They encourage students to be active and responsive in learning, understand the obstacles students face in accessing online education, and provide emotional and mental support to students. Public service motivation is an important factor in forming teachers' commitment to providing quality education, even in extraordinary situations such as a pandemic. This intrinsic motivation encourages teachers to make positive contributions to students and society, beyond their routine duties. The high level of involvement of teachers in ensuring the continuity of the learning process and providing optimal educational services reflects the positive impact of PSM in improving their performance.

H₂: Public service motivation influences employee performance.

The standard regression weight value that measures the influence of Public Services (PSM) on organizational performance is 0.052, with a critical ratio value greater than 1.96, namely 2.799. These results indicate that PSM has a significant positive impact on employee performance with an estimated value of 0.294. The results of this study are in line with the findings of several previous studies, such as Brewer et al., (1998); Naff & Crum, (1999); Qi & Wang, (2018); Ritz, (2009); Torfing & Bentzen, (2020); Xin, (2022); Zhu & Wu, (2016); Zubair et al., (2021) also concluded that public service motivation influences employee performance.

Public service motivation is a concept that refers to an individual's intrinsic desire to contribute to serving the needs of society or the public interest. The most significant and relevant factor to be improved in this context is the dimension of self-sacrifice, with community service as the most important indicator. Furthermore, the dimension of compassion also needs to be improved, especially in terms of patient serving the community and empathy in overcoming problems that occur. Then, interest in policymaking and interest in the work environment also become the focus of improvement. Finally, responsibility or commitment to the public interest, with indicators such as working sincerely and providing maximum service, needs to be increased. Teachers with strong public service motivation tend to be more dedicated to providing quality education services, innovating in designing lesson plans, adapting to changes in technology and learning methods, and continuing to provide optimal educational services.

Employee Performance

In this study, the main attention was focused on the impact of the Learning from Home program, employee innovation, and public service motivation on employee performance. In the educational context, employee performance involves effectiveness in delivering material, interaction with students, virtual learning management, and the ability to adapt to new technology. The relationship between these three factors significantly influences employee performance in providing quality education.

Performance measurement is one way to assess the extent of its effectiveness. Organizations have very important goals and objectives, which include the ability to set goals and objectives, as well as ways to improve overall employee performance (Pang & Lu, 2018). S. Kim (2005) assesses organizational performance through three main dimensions, namely internal efficiency, external effectiveness, and internal justice. Han and Hong (2019) also stated that organizational performance is influenced by factors such as organizational constraints, knowledge sharing, security, and physical conditions.

According to Elbanna et al., (2016) , employee performance attributes in public sector organizations include operational efficiency, effectiveness in achieving organizational goals, and service quality. Employee performance measurement is based on four factors based on the Brewer and Selden (2000) scale, which include service quality, customer satisfaction, cost reduction commitment, and timeliness. S. Kim (2004) defines employee performance as a concept that includes various aspects such as needs, goals, timeliness, cost, and accuracy. To control the influence of other factors on employee performance, an understanding of the transformation process and knowledge of the targets to be achieved are also considered very important (Nitzl et al., 2019).

In assessing the performance of public employees, Brewer and Selden (2000) suggest three main aspects to consider, namely efficiency, effectiveness and fairness. Bratton (2017) highlights factors that affect employee performance, including quality of work, amount of work, punctuality in completing work, ability to collaborate, and ability to carry out tasks. Chun and Rainey (2005) identified various elements that influence employee performance in organizations, including managerial effectiveness, customer service orientation, productivity,

and the quality of the work they do. All of these factors have a significant impact on employee work outcomes in the organizational context.

H₃: Implementation of the Learning from Home program affects employee performance.

In a study conducted by Rafiq et al., (2021) , it was found that policy implementation has an important role in determining employee performance levels. The results of this study indicate that the quality of policy implementation significantly influences employee performance (Sembiring, 2011). There is a positive relationship between the level of employee performance and good policy implementation. The policy implementation process involves the interpretation and application of the aims and objectives of the policy. Furthermore, implementation is also a key stage in the policy cycle that considers how the policy will be implemented, which necessitates cooperation between policy beneficiaries and implementing organizations to implement appropriate procedures and techniques (Khan & Khandaker, 2016). Policy implementation within an organization can serve as a measure of employee performance (Peris-Ortiz et al., 2019). According to Sadyrova et al., (2021) , the effectiveness of policy implementation will ultimately have an impact on performance, both at the individual, group, and organizational levels as a whole. Therefore, the implementation of policies within an organization or entity will have a significant impact or influence on the performance of employees and the organization as a whole.

The Home Learning Program provides an opportunity for employees, especially teachers, to take part in training and improve their abilities. This program encourages employees to improve their skills to support the learning process in the digital era. The results of the analysis show that the implementation of the Home Learning Program has a significant positive influence on employee performance, as measured in a standard regression of 0.051 with a critical ratio value greater than 1.96, namely 4.341. This means that the implementation of the Home Learning Program affects employee performance. In addition, the estimate of 0.221 shows that employee performance can influence the success of implementing the Home Learning Program.

The implementation of the Home Learning Program is expected to improve employee performance, which is reflected in various dimensions and indicators. The most significant and relevant factors in improving efficiency indicators are the ability to complete tasks properly within the specified time limit (0.813), solve problems in the work environment (0.894), and achieve peak performance in developing individual careers (0.933). Furthermore, in terms of effectiveness, indicators that need to be improved are the level of achievement of the planned goals (0.910) and the ability to complete tasks by the goals set (0.920). Employee performance in the Learn from Home Program covers a variety of responsibilities, such as achieving educational goals, interacting with students, and adapting to technology and its impact on learning outcomes. In addition, the impact of the implementation of the Learning from Home Program on employee innovation and public service motivation will also be measured by improving employee performance. A teacher who actively participates in the Learn from Home Program applies innovative teaching methods, and is motivated by good public service, has a greater chance of achieving success in education.

CONCLUSION

Implementation of home learning programs, employee innovation, and public service motivation are interrelated factors that play an important role in improving employee performance, particularly in the education sector. Understanding the interactions between these four factors allows us to identify strategies that can enhance digital education transformation and deliver high-quality education. The transformation of digital education provides opportunities for teachers to utilize technology to develop their abilities and improve the learning process in the digital era. Teachers can take advantage of various digital platforms and tools to provide more effective and relevant training. It also allows teachers to be more creative in their teaching methods and helps students with different learning styles. Although this transformation has had a positive impact, some challenges need to be overcome, such as limited internet access and difficulties in using digital technology.

Public service motivation plays a key role in supporting this transformation. A teacher who is motivated to provide the best service to students will have a stronger determination to overcome obstacles that may arise and create meaningful learning experiences. Education transformation in the digital era can have a positive impact on teacher performance. However, to optimize this impact, support is needed in the form of adequate infrastructure, development of technological skills, innovation in education, and increased motivation for public service among teachers. Digital education transformation not only changes student learning experiences but also creates a learning environment that is dynamic and able to adapt to changes in society. This shows that understanding the role of motivation, innovation and implementation of programs such as the Learning from Home Program in the educational context is very important in improving the quality of education provided to students.

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